

Effect of *Baboona (Matricaria chamomile)* in the management of Primary Dysmenorrhea (*Usre Tams*): A Case series

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ABSTRACT

Dysmenorrhea is one of the most common Gynecologic complaints. In the present KIUsenario it affects half of all the adolescent females and represents the leading cause of school or college absenteeism. Hence, is most common in the age group of 20 and 24 years. The management mainly includes the use of NSAIDs and COX-2 inhibitors. However, the treatment only provides temporary relief to the patient. According to the *Unani* classical literature *usre tams* occurs due to stagnation of menstrual blood secondary to cervical obstruction and causes painful menstrual period. A number of therapeutic interventions are used to manage the pain during menstruation, including the role of *Ilaj Bil Dawa*, *Ilaj bil Ghiza* and *Ilaj Bil Tadbeer* etc. In the vast literature available in Unani texts, there are number of drugs available which are recommended for the management of dysmenorrhea which possess properties like muhallile auram, dafae tashannuj, mudire haiz, mudire bol etc, among all Baboona (*matricaria chamomila*) has long been used mainly as anti-inflammatory agent. Recent trials have also shown that chamomile a chemical constituents derived from *matricaria chamomila* appeared to have those similar action of NSAIDS, has inhibition of cox 2 enzyme activity This article is a comprehensive overview of dysmenorrhea and its management through *Unani* medicine.

Keywords: *Usre Tams*, Dysmenorrhea, Women, NSAIDs. *Matricaria chamomilla*.

INTRODUCTION

Menstrual disorders are the commonest presentation in adolescence. 75% of adolescent females experience some problems associated with menstruation.¹ dysmenorrhea is one of the commonest complaints. Patient experiences severe painful cramping sensation in the lower abdomen which is associated with sweating, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea just before the onset of menstruation during the menses. Affected women describes the pain as sharp intermittent spasm usually in the suprapubic area & may transfer to the back of the legs or the lower back. Pain usually develops within hours of the start of the menstruation and going to peaks as flow become heaviest during the first day or two of the cycle² In the Unani system of medicine, *Usre tams* is the term used for dysmenorrhea or painful menstruation, it is also known as *dard-e- rahem* or *aujaur rahem*³

According to Greek philosopher Hippocrates, dysmenorrhea occurs due to cessation of menstrual blood flow secondarily due to cervical obstruction and thereby causes painful menstruation¹. Another concept mentioned as per the classical Unani texts is excessive accumulation of humors (*balgham* and *sauda*) which makes the blood viscous. Therefore, perfusion of blood into small vessels become difficult resulting in dysmenorrhea.⁴

According to shaikhur Rayees Abu Ali Husain bin Abdullah bin sina *usre tams* occurs due to obstruction in the menstrual blood flow. he also described that if the menstrual blood is balanced in quality and quantity, the cycle is regular. if the menstruation is irregular and abnormal, it may cause many diseases like amenorrhoea and oligomenorrhoea.⁵

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Hakeem Ajmal Khan a renowned Unani clinician has mentioned that the patient may become comatose or senseless due to the extreme pain. She may also experience heaviness in the pelvic area and pain in the inner thighs as well in the flanks and sometimes in lower back area. This pain mainly develops before the onset of menstruation^{6,7}

An eminent Unani physician Zakaria Razi used the term *aujaur rehm* for dysmenorrhea and discussed the cause of *aujaur rehm* as *zaufe rehm*, *sartane rehm* and *ehtebase rehm*.⁸

In spite of prevalence of disease of mass level, the choice of treatment available are NSAIDS like Mefenamic acid, Ibuprofen, Tiaprofenic acid etc. Out of these Mefenamic acid is widely used for managing the pain of dysmenorrhea as it also improves menstruation related irregularities (Heavy Menstrual Bleeding).⁹ The mechanism of action of these drugs is that it decreases the production of prostaglandin by cyclooxygenase enzymes and inhibit prostaglandin receptor in the uterus.¹⁰ Though the drugs are highly efficacious many a times patient presents with complaints of indigestion, headaches and drowsiness. Such situation warrants some alternative arrangement for the treatment of dysmenorrhea.

In Unani system of medicine, the treatment modalities are categorized as *ilaj bit tadbeer*, *ilaj bit Ghiza*, *ilaj bit dawa*, *ilaj bit yad*. Therefore, the treatment is planned according to the dietary habits, clinical manifestations, and identifying the *mizaj* of the patient. Since the majority of the females presenting with dysmenorrhea have excessive accumulation of *Khilte Balgham* and *sauda* hence the treatment *ilaj biz zid* is applied.

There are a number of drugs available in the unani literature such as *baboona*, *nakhoona*, *rewandchini*, *abhal*, *hiltet*, *soya*, *kalonji*, *hulba*, *gule surkh*, *saunf* etc which are recommended for the management of dysmenorrhea.¹¹ These drugs possess the clinical properties like *muhallile auram*, *dafae tashannuj*(antispasmodic), *mudire haiz*(emmenagogue), *mudire bol* and *musakkin* etc. Among all of the mentioned drugs *Baboona* (*Matricaria chamomilla*) has long been used mainly as an anti-inflammatory (*muhallile auram*) agent. It was

also found to have antiseptic (*dafae Taffun*), and antispasmodic properties (*dafae tashannuj*).¹²

Mechanism of action of the drug: *Matricaria chamomilla*, is one of the most widely used medicinal plants¹³ According to studies on chamomile so far, its effects on stomach pain, irritable bowel syndrome, insomnia, and wound healing have been confirmed.¹⁴ Pure Azoline is one of the effective compounds in this plant that has anti-inflammatory and antiseptic effects. Apigenin and methoxy-coumarin have antispasmodic properties.¹⁵ The anti-inflammatory effects of Chamomile are mostly due to compounds such as *Matrisin* and *Bisabolol*.¹⁶ There is also evidence of flavonoids with similar functions to benzodiazepines and phytoestrogens in Chamomile, which has positive sedative effects¹⁷ It also appeared to have actions similar to those of NSAIDS, and has inhibitions of COX-2 enzyme activity. Seeing the efficacy of the drug in Menstruation related pain *baboona* has been selected for trial in the management of dysmenorrhea.¹⁸

Methodology 5 cases of Primary dysmenorrhea were randomly selected from the patients visiting the Gynecology OPD of Ajmal Khan Tibbiya college and hospital. The patients were subjected to history taking and clinical examination to diagnose primary dysmenorrhea. Both married and unmarried subjects in the age group of 15-25 years with painful menstruation regular or irregular cycle, with one or more symptoms like low backache, nausea, vomiting or diarrhea, medial or anterior thigh pain were included in the study. The patients with associated pelvic pathology, malignancy, or infectious conditions were not selected for the pilot study.

The treatment protocol was for 3 consecutive cycles.

Powdered *Baboona* (*Matricaria chamomile*) was given 6g in divided doses twice a day orally starting from 2days prior to her LMP and continued for the first 3days of menses. The patients were assessed for relief in menstrual pain and associated symptoms via VAS Scoring (Visual Analogue Scale) and improvement in their daily activities through quality of life (QOL)questionnaire.

Drug preparation and Dispensing: Dried *Baboona* (whole plant) was purchased from GMP certified

company Dawakhana Tibbiya College, AMU Aligarh. The drug was identified and authenticated in the department of Ilmul Advia (Pharmacology) AMU Aligarh. The drug was finely ground and filled in zip lock bags. The patients were called for follow up twice a month to record VAS scoring and drug dispensing once before and once after menstruation for 3 consecutive cycles. The patients were evaluated for change in severity of pain & overall improvement in dysmenorrhea and associated symptoms. The following are the case scenarios;

Case 1: 20-year-old unmarried female complaining of cramping lower abdomen pain and a low back ache that began shortly before menstruation and persisted for a single day came to the OPD of Niswan Wa Qabalat. Her problems began two years after she turned fourteen, the time of her menarche. The menstrual cycle was normal with intervals of 28-30 days. During her menstruation, she was unable to attend college and turned to medicines for pain relief.

She was included in the study after routine investigations and USG pelvis (to rule out pelvic pathology). Before starting the treatment, her VAS score was recorded as 8 which reduced to 2 after 3 cycles of treatment. Her quality-of-life scale was 0 and after treatment it was recorded as 4. All her subjective complaints were also reduced.

Case 2: A 25-year-old unmarried girl came to the outpatient department. She complained of significant lower abdomen discomfort one day before and on the first day of her period, as well as low back pain that started the day her period started and went away in a day or two. She mentioned that she had a history of taking analgesics intermittently, and her mother has voiced similar concerns. Her VAS score before the treatment was 7 and after the successful treatment of 12 weeks her VAS score become 2 and her QOL score also improved from 0 to 3 after 3 consecutive cycles.

Case No. 3:

This case was of an 18-year-old married girl, complaining of excruciating lower abdomen pain, low back ache, vomiting, and giddiness. Her menstruation extended for a duration of 12 days and began to have

these complaints from the year following menarche. She was in so much pain that she was unable to leave the house to study and was bedridden for two whole days. There was a prior history of regular hospital admissions during the menstrual cycle with intravenous fluid infusion and analgesic injection. She was counselled and medication was started as per the protocol. Her VAS score prior to the treatment was 9 which reduced to 1 post treatment. QOL value also improved from a pre-treatment score of 1 to 2.

Case 4: A 25-year-old woman who has had dysmenorrhea for 11 years, with symptoms starting two years after menarche. She reported multiple instances of missing class due to pain that starts at the onset of menstrual flow and goes away entirely in a day. She had a family history of primary dysmenorrhea and used to take analgesics for pain alleviation. Her VAS score before the treatment was 7 and after completion of duration for 3 cycles her VAS score becomes 1 and her QOL score was 0 and after completion of treatment for 3 consecutive cycle her QOL questionnaire score become 4.

Case 5: An eighteen-year-old girl came to our outpatient department five years ago complaining of excruciating lower abdomen pain during her menstruation. Pain lasts for two days and starts when the menstrual flow starts. She also reported having giddiness and a low back soreness. Her cycles, which lasted for four to five days, were regular and had an interval of 28 -30 days. used analgesics to alleviate pain. There had been no known relevant family history. Her VAS score before the treatment was 8 and after the treatment of 3 month duration her VAS score become 0. And quality of life score was 1 and after treatment it become 4

Result of intervention: The Unani drug Baboona was given to the patients for 3 consecutive cycles. The subjective parameters related to dysmenorrhea such as abdominal pain, pain in the thigh area, vomiting, constipation, dysuria and malaise were assessed in all the 5 cases. All the symptoms were found to be improved after taking the test drug. The objective parameters include Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for pain was also improved. The quality-of-life questionnaire score also increased following 3 months of therapy. Patient was called every 15 days during

treatment for drug dispensing and compliance to drug. The patients studied were kept on follow up without treatment for next 3 consecutive cycles after the treatment to note relapse of symptoms. Participants did not report any adverse effects or symptoms with the oral consumption of powdered chamomile. Compliance to the oral intake of powdered chamomile was good. No major side effect has been reported in this study

Discussion: Despite the widespread occurrence of diseases, there is currently no permanent cure for dysmenorrhea; therefore, the options for treating the condition in the existing medical system are somewhat limited and also have adverse effects. Eminent Unani Scholar described various Unani formulations in the authentic books for the treatment of dysmenorrhea. All the cases chosen for study showed improvement in both the subjective as well as objective parameters. As per the unani concept of management the powdered baboona has the properties of antispasmodic, anti-inflammatory and analgesic which relieves the pain associated with dysmenorrhea.¹⁹ This has been validated by present case series that Unani formulation is effective in treating pain related to menstruation. Furthermore, there as per the recent trials it is presumed that it causes a 50% decrease in prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) levels, which leads to the suppression of COX activity₂ and in turn decreases menstrual pain.

The patient's safety parameters were also assessed & any concomitant toxicity on liver, kidney was also kept in watch through the kidney function test and Liver function tests. There was no apparent and observable adverse effect during the study and at the end of the study. Similarly, the drug has no observable adverse effect on blood routine investigations also.

Conclusion: Even though disorders are common, dysmenorrhea presently has no known permanent cure; as a result, the alternatives available to treat the ailment within the current medical system are fairly restricted. Perhaps some have negative impacts as well.

In the Unani medical system, a number of effective and safe drugs have been found to be helpful for dysmenorrhea such as Baboona (*Matricaria chamomile*) by virtues of its properties in relieving

symptoms of dysmenorrhea.²⁰ further studied are required to conclusively prove the effect of *Matricaria chamomile* which can be used safely and effectively in relieving pain associated with dysmenorrhea.

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